

METAL GAS BOTTLES REINFORCED WITH

A FILAMENT-WOUND COMPOSITE LAYER

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Summary

In the present work the results of proof and burst tests of filament-wound steel-lined gas bottles fabricated with aramid fibers are presented and discussed. Strains in the metal liner and composite layer were measured during pressurization in the circumferencial and axial directions. Acoustic emission activity was also monitored during the tests. Burst tests showed that only if liner and composite layer thicknesses are correctly dimensioned, the failure of the gas bottle occurs according to acceptance standards requirements. All measured strains start increasing linearly during pressurization and simultaneously deviate from linearity, possibly indicating metal liner yield initiation. The metal and composite hoop strain plots versus pressure exhibit different slopes, although they were predicted to coincide on the basis of a theoretical elastic analysis. The acoustic emission starting pressure was generally comprised between 70% and 75% of burst pressure. It is shown that the acoustic emission activity is mainly due to fibers failures and is related to the conditions of the filament-wound layer.

Introduction

A study was undertaken in order to show the technical feasibility of high-pressure gas bottles made of an internal metal liner reinforced on the cylindrical part with a layer of composite material. The scope was to obtain methane gas bottles for automotive application of lower weight than the present all-metal types.

The weight gain that may be obtained in comparison with all-metal bottles with similar performances is a function of bottle size and burst pressure. In the case studied in this paper, such gain was 32% - 35%, whereas with other kinds of bottles it is possible to attain a 40% gain (1) (2).

In the present work the experimental results of proof and burst tests of filament-wound steel-lined gas bottles fabricated with aramid fibers are presented and discussed. These data are examined to determine the reliability of theoretical models for bottle behaviour proposed in a previous work (2) and to verify the possibility of utilizing AE monitoring as a method to evaluate the correct fabrication of metal-composite gas bottles

Materials, fabrication and testing

The organic fiber Kevlar 49 (DuPont de Nemours, 7 200 denier) was used as reinforcing materials. The naked fibers were filament-wound over the cylindrical part of a metal gas bottle utilizing a modified parallel lathe. The metal liner, produced by FABER Spa, Cividale del Friuli (UD), Italy, was made of 35 Mn B5F steel (828 N/mm² yield strength and 920 N/mm² tensile strength). Gas bottles dimensions are reported in fig. 1; design service pressure and burst pressure were respectively 30 MPa and 75 MPa.

The filament-winding was accomplished over the cylindrical zone of the bottle so that the single-end strand was oriented in the hoop direction. This fact, together with the use of naked fibers for maximum weight saving, involves the absence of contribution to axial resistance on the part of the fibers. During filament-winding, the Kevlar 49 strand was subjected to a tension of ~ 100 N. The filament-wound layer may be considered a Kevlar 49/air monolayer composite with $V_f \approx 0.72$. The theoretical tensile strength of such a composite is $\sigma_{1cu} = 2\,000$ N/mm², the elastic modulus $E_1 = 93\,600$ N/mm² and the density 1 000 Kg/m³. Actual tensile strength, though, is quite lower because of inevitable imperfections in the winding and physical contact between fibers; previous works (1) (2) suggested a possible actual tensile strength of 1.200 N/mm².

In fig.2 a group of metal-composite gas bottles is shown; the presence of a carbon fiber filament wound metal-lined gas bottle, prepared as an example, may be noticed in the center.

The composite wall thickness was generally 2 mm, according to the indications of the hybrid bottle elasto-plastic behaviour models discussed in (1) (2). In one case the wall thickness was deliberately overdimensioned at 4 mm.

The pressure tests were conducted using water mixed with soluble oil to pressurize the gas bottles at a constant rate of ~ 10 MPa/min. Each gas bottle was subjected to a first pressure cycle up to 60 MPa (80% of the expected failure pressure) and then, after AE transducer removal, to a second pressure cycle

Fig 1 - Metal-composite gas bottle design

Fig. 2 - Metal-composite gas bottles. Note in the middle a carbon fiber filament-wound metal-lined gas bottle.

up to final failure.

During the first pressure cycle of each bottle, acoustic emission activity was monitored through an AE resonant transducer (resonant frequency = 140 kHz) placed on the bottom of the gas bottle with adhesive tape and acoustically coupled with ultrasonic couplant. AE signals were preamplified by 40 dB, high-pass filtered (cut-off frequency = 50 kHz) and fed to an AE instrumentation system for signal conditioning and analysis. The instrumentation was set for all tests with 50 dB amplification and 1.0 V threshold level. The AE parameters recorded as a function of pressure were total AE counts, N_{ta} , and event count rate \dot{N}_e . AE detection was carried out in order to verify the applicability of this technique for non destructive testing and quality evaluation of filament-wound metal-lined composite gas bottles. During both pressure cycles of each gas bottle, axial and hoop strains in the metal liner and hoop strain in the composite layer were measured through electrical strain gauges.

Results and discussion

Burst tests

In tab.I the results of the proof and burst tests are summarized. Different failure modes were observed according to the different characteristics of the metal-composite structure. In the last four columns of the table the calculated values of the metal axial stress at failure σ_{am} , the AE starting pressure, the yield pressure predicted by elasto-plastic models

Tab. I - Experimental results

Id.	Liner thick. (mm)	Type of composite	Comp. thick. (mm)	Type of failure	Burst press. (MPa)	σ_{am} at failure (N/mm ²)	AE starting pressure		Predicted yield press.		σ_{1c} at failure (N/mm ²)	
							(MPa)	% *	"A"	"B"	"A"	"B"
							1	2.70	Kevlar 49	2.0	axial	75
2	2.50	Kevlar 49	2.0	hoop	68	911	49.5	73	49.0	40.0	1038	1287
3	2.70	Kevlar 49	2.0	axial	73	920	55.0	75	51.5	42.0	1125	1390
4	2.95	Carbon HM	2.0	fiber	53	601	53.0	100	66.0	52.5	530	540
5	2.95	Kevlar 49	2.0	none	>77	874	54.0	<70	55.5	45.5	1130	1417
6	2.50	Kevlar 49	4.0	axial	69	924	62.0	50	62.0	48.0	490	650

* Percentage of actual burst pressure.

"A" and "B" (2), and the composite hoop stress at failure σ_{1c} predicted by models "A" and "B" are indicated.

In fig. 3 examples of bottles that failed under hoop and axial stress are shown.

The carbon fiber reinforced bottle failed under hoop stress at a pressure notably lower than nominal burst pressure (53 MPa << 75 MPa). This was due to early fiber failure caused by the deterioration of the brittle HM carbon fibers during the filament-winding (2). Better mechanical behaviour is expected from Kevlar, HS carbon and glass fibers.

Considering the behaviour of the Kevlar wound bottles, it is possible to note that the thickness of the composite layer is a critical parameter for the type of bottle failure: an oversizing of the composite layer may produce an axial type of failure which is not acceptable according to international standards for gas bottles. This is what happened to bottle n. 6 with 4 mm Kevlar layer, whereas bottle n.2 failed under hoop stress because its 2 mm thick composite layer couldn't withstand the hoop stress σ_{1c} at the pressure of 68 MPa. At this pressure, σ_{am} for bottle n. 2 was lower than the metal ultimate strength (911 N/mm² < 920 N/mm²).

Also the metal liner thickness is critical for the type of bottle failure: an undersizing of the metal liner may produce an axial failure at pressures lower than the nominal burst pressure. This is what happened to bottles n. 1, n. 3 and n. 6.

From the experimental results, it is evident that the critical stresses for a hybrid gas bottle are metal axial stress σ_{am} and composite hoop stress σ_{1c} in the fiber direction. The former must be lower than the metal ultimate strength up to final failure and the latter may be higher than the composite actual ultimate strength σ_{1cu} only after burst pressure is reached. It is worth remarking that σ_{1cu} must be evaluated through experimental tests carried out on hybrid gas bottles prepared with the actual fabrication technology.(1).

(a)

(b)

Fig. 3 - Gas bottles failed under (a) hoop stress and (b) axial stress

Strain measurements

In figs. 4-7 the metal axial and hoop strains and the composite hoop strain, measured during the pressure tests, are reported as functions of applied pressure for bottles n.1, n.2 and n.6. In the same figures the continuous and dotted lines represent the metal and composite theoretical hoop strains ϵ_{tm} and ϵ_{1c} (expected to be coincident) predicted by models "A" and "B" and the metal axial theoretical strain ϵ_{am} . In figs. 5-7 the AE activity is also reported as a function of pressure.

The experimental strains increase linearly in the first part of the strain pressure plot as is shown in fig.4 for bottle n.2 pressurized to 30 MPa. Metal axial strain ϵ_{am} seems to be in good agreement with the theoretical prediction (figs.4-7), whereas metal and composite hoop strains ϵ_{tm} and ϵ_{1c} on one hand increase with different slopes (i.e. they do not coincide as expected on the basis of theoretical elastic analysis) and on the other hand they are in poor agreement with the theoretical predictions: in the elastic field ϵ_{tm} , which is always higher than ϵ_{1c} , in some cases is lower than the theoretical value (fig.5) and in some other cases is higher (fig.6 and 7). Moreover ϵ_{1c} does not start increasing as soon as pressure is applied but presents an incubation period, as is shown in fig.8.

These observations suggest on one hand that to start stressing the composite layer it is first necessary for the metal to deform until all slack in the filament-wound naked fibers is recovered (incubation period of ϵ_{1c}); this inconvenience may be overcome by filament-winding at a high tension. The difference in slope between ϵ_{tm} and ϵ_{1c} in the elastic field, on the other hand, seems to indicate that in the Kevlar-air composite the fibers continue to settle and adjust during pressurization because of the absence of resin that would homogeneously distribute the load through the composite thickness. This phenomenon witnesses a poor utilization of the composite and is greatly enhanced in the case of composite oversizing (fig.7). The use of fiber-resin composite should reduce the slope difference between the ϵ_{tm} and ϵ_{1c} plots by allowing for a better metal-composite congruence and a better utilization of the composite layer.

Starting from a certain value of pressure, experimental strain plots (ϵ_{tm} , ϵ_{1c} and ϵ_{am}) deviate from linearity, indicating the occurrence of yield deformation in the metal liner. The experimental yield hoop strain of the metal coincides approximately with the range of values predicted by models "A" and "B" (figs.5-7). Because of the large approximation, though, it is not possible to prefer one model or the other on the basis of these results. A better judgment on the models as concerns yield hoop strain prediction might be given in the case of a more congruent behaviour between metal and composite; this is what the authors intend to verify on gas bottles reinforced with a fiber/resin composite layer.

In conclusion the experimental strains plots display, although ϵ_{tm} and ϵ_{1c} do not coincide as predicted theoretically, a qualitatively similar behaviour: all strains start increasing linearly and simultaneously deviate from linearity as soon as yielding occurs.

Fig. 4 - Gas bottle n.2: strain versus pressure. Maximum pressure 30 MPa.

Fig. 5 - Gas bottle n.2: strain versus pressure. Burst test. A, B: elasto-plastic models AE: acoustic emission

Fig. 6 - Gas bottle n.1: strain versus pressure. Burst test. A, B: elasto-plastic models AE: acoustic emission

Acoustic emission detection

For all tests, in the first part of the pressure cycles no AE was detected; the initiation of significant AE activity was observed only well after the onset and the development of yield deformation in the metal liner, as indicated by strain measurements (figs.5-7).

The AE starting pressure (tab.I) was generally comprised between 70% and 76% of burst pressure. Only in two cases AE started at a pressure very near burst pressure. The first was the case of the carbon fiber

Fig.7 - Gas bottle n.6: strain versus pressure. Burst test. A, B: elasto-plastic model; AE: acoustic emission

Fig.8 - Gas bottle n.5: strain versus pressure. Maximum pressure 4 MPa.

reinforced hybrid bottle (bottle n.4) that exhibited an early failure due to fiber breakage, AE starting pressure practically coincided with burst pressure. In the second case, the AE starting pressure was 90% of 90% of burst pressure (bottle n.6): this bottle was the one with 4 mm thick Kevlar layer.

As concerns the cause of the AE activity detected during the proof tests of filament-wound hybrid pressure vessels, the possible AE sources could be, according to (3) and (4): (A) the cracking of the matrix parallel to the direction of the fibers as a result of local stresses perpendicular to the fiber direction, which occurs in the biaxially loaded composite structure; (B) events occurring in the metal liner such as plastic deformation or crack forming and growth; (C) the almost simultaneous failure of several fibers occurring at several particular locations of high stress throughout the composite layer.

The activity produced by the first kind of source should consist of low amplitude, numerous AE events resulting in quasi-continuous AE observed very soon in the load history of the hybrid gas bottle (3) (4). In our case no matrix was present in the filament-wound layer and the possible alternative as source of early and quasi-continuous AE, i.e. fiber friction, was not operating as no AE was detected before 70% of the burst pressure.

The AE generated by the metal liner plastic deformation should be particularly evident at yield onset and then decrease or gradually disappear, as reported by various research workers (5) . In our case, no AE activity was detected at yield onset, signalled by the deviation from linearity of the experimental strain plots. AE activity was observed only well after yield initiation and development and kept increasing with pressure. This fact suggests that the total AE system gains were too low to be sensitive to any AE generated by events in the metal liner; the same observation was also made in (3).

The AE generated by fiber failures should consist of large amplitude (i.e. high energy) discrete AE events resulting in burst type AE observed rather late in the load history of the gas bottle (3). This is what happened in our case where the step-like AE plot of figs. 5-7 testifies the late burst type activity consisting of high-energy AE events.

It is therefore possible to attribute the AE activity detected during the proof tests to fiber breakages. If this hypothesis is accepted it is also possible to explain the different AE behaviour of gas bottles n.4 and n.6. In the first case fiber failures were quite precocious, developed rapidly throughout the filament-wound layer and immediately led to gas bottle burst. In this case AE starting pressure may well coincide with burst pressure (tab. I).

In the second case, the high composite thickness (4 mm) reduces, at same pressure level, the composite hoop stress σ_{1c} in the fiber direction; it is natural therefore for the first fiber failures to occur at a higher pressure and for AE to start at a pressure quite near to the burst pressure (tab. I).

The AE from the 2 mm Kevlar layer hybrid gas bottles starts at pressure values quite similar in all cases, especially if expressed in terms of percentage of actual burst pressure (70 - 76 %). The last consideration, together with the previous observations, indicate that the starting of AE

activity is strictly related to the conditions of the filament-wound layer. It seems therefore possible to use AE techniques in order to identify the variations in the fabrication process of hybrid gas bottles, e.g. composite thickness changes or filament-wound fiber damage. AE methods may, in this case, be employed as routine tests to evaluate whether or not the composite structure was correctly fabricated.

Conclusions

From the above considerations, the following conclusions may be drawn:

- The critical stresses for the behaviour of a metal-composite gas bottle are the metal axial stress σ_{am} and the composite hoop stress σ_{1c} in the fiber direction.
- Experimental metal axial strain ϵ_{am} seems to be in good agreement with the theoretical prediction, whereas metal and composite hoop strains ϵ_{tm} and ϵ_{1c} do not coincide as expected on the basis of theoretical elastic analysis. The latter result seems to indicate that in Kevlar-air composite, the naked fibers continue to settle and adjust during pressurization involving a poor utilization of the composite.
- The initiation of significant AE activity was observed only well after the onset and development of metal yielding and AE starting pressure was generally comprised between 70% and 76% of burst pressure. The AE activity is mainly due to fiber breakages occurring at several particular locations of high stress throughout the composite layer and seems to be closely related to the conditions of the filament-wound layer. The latter point makes it possible for AE techniques to be used for the identification of variations in the fabrication process of metal-composite gas bottles.

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Bibliography

- (1) I. Crivelli Visconti, R. Teti, "Considerazioni sulla progettazione e realizzazione di bombole ibride in metallo-composito", Quaderni di Ricerca dell'Ist. di Tecnologie, CUEN, Napoli, Oct. 1984.
- (2) I. Crivelli Visconti, R. Teti, "Bombole per metano con impiego di materiali compositi", Proc. II Metanauto - Int. Congr. Exh. on the Use of Methane in the Transport Sector, Bologna, Italy, 21-23 Sept. 1984.
- (3) M. A. Hamstad, "Variabilities Detected by Acoustic Emission from Filament-wound Aramid Fiber/epoxy Composite Pressure Vessels", Proc. 24th. Int. Instrumentation Symp., Albuquerque, New Mexico, May 1-5, 1978.
- (4) M. A. Hamstad, T. T. Chiao, "A Physical Mechanism for the Early Acoustic Emission in an Organic-Fiber/Epoxy Pressure Vessel", SAMPE Quarterly, Vol. 5, N. 2, 1974, p. 22.
- (5) H. L. Dunegan, A. T. Green, "Factors Affecting Acoustic Emission Response from Materials", pp. 100 - 113 in Acoustic Emission, ASTM STP 505, ASTM, Philadelphia, 1972.